

Achieving Net Zero: Integrating Climate Justice into the Pathway to Sustainable Research

Authors: Molly MacRae, Charlotte Pascoe

“Net Zero is a societal challenge which requires sustained collaboration and cooperation”

In our pursuit of transformational change to meet the net zero challenge we also have an opportunity to establish a fairer, more equitable society. A bold vision for net zero therefore encompasses a just social transformation alongside technical solutions.

Applying climate justice to the UKRI journey to Net Zero DRI requires ensuring those who can reasonably bear the burden adopt early and strong mitigation policies and changes. This requires a proportionate response from institutions to do what they can to reduce their carbon footprint whilst also considering the wider societal impacts of the actions taken to do so.

Defining climate justice

Climate justice is a term that recognizes that although global warming is a global crisis, its effects are not felt evenly around the world. Climate justice is an aspect of environmental justice and focuses on the equitable distribution of the burdens of climate change and the efforts to mitigate them. It has been described as encompassing "a set of rights and obligations, which corporations, individuals and governments have towards those vulnerable people who will be in a way significantly disproportionately affected by climate change."¹

We should use our mandate as UKRI to lead the way to doing what is best for society and our planet, and the UKRI journey to net zero DRI is a valuable opportunity to do this.

The role of UKRI DRI in the big picture

There is precedent for including social justice within the operation of research practices, and research enabled by a net zero DRI should be no different. We cannot view the UKRI DRI transition to net zero in isolation: it should be assessed in the context of its impacts on wider society. For example, DRI is increasingly used to accurately simulate real-world scenarios in replacement of mechanical laboratories. Though advancements like this create a need for DRI growth, this growth leads to a large reduction in emissions compared to the technology it is replacing. This highlights the importance of not limiting DRI growth for the sake of limiting emissions but holding a holistic perspective towards our goal of Net Zero.

¹ [Climate justice - Wikipedia](#)

Both institutional and individual responses to the Net Zero challenge should carefully consider the impacts in wider society. Institutional net zero policies should not block the wider societal pathway to net zero, for instance by consuming a disproportionate quantity of limited renewable energy resources. Similarly, the carbon requirements set on individuals using DRI for research should not interfere with the optimal operation of such equipment (e.g. individual carbon budgets interfering with facility-wide green scheduling.)

UKRI must take a proactive approach to ensuring that net zero policy does not disrupt research programmes and that prioritisation of low carbon investment and purchasing options does not have a disproportionate negative impact.

The journey to net zero computing requires transformational change which can deliver huge benefits as part of the broader transformation to a new generation of digitally enabled research. The transition to sustainable research computing must follow and support the national transition to a sustainable economy, as outlined by the Climate Change Committee (CCC) balanced pathway to net zero.²

Clear communication

Communicating clearly to the wide, diverse audience that makes up UKRI DRI users from across all research councils is vital for an equitable approach to reaching net zero. It is not sufficient to just 'green' our current technologies as these discriminate against particular groups. Furthermore, these do not capture the future projection of DRI use as it is increasingly adopted by more disciplines that have not typically used DRI in the past.

UKRI should use its capacity in social sciences, arts and humanities, and in economics, to understand the range of societal views, as well as the avenues of consensus which open-up potential for accelerating transition and the emerging discords which can block or reverse change.

A recommendation from the Net Zero DRI project suggests UKRI should employ specialist communications and engagement expert/s whose sole responsibility is to work with the environmental sustainability group to ensure messages are clear and engaging for a diverse audience.

Steps should be taken to minimise barriers to the adoption of potential efficiencies arising from new technologies in hardware and software, for example by ensuring adequate cross over between researchers and experts of technology. We must ensure the introduction of new technologies is matched by information that is reliable and relevant, appropriate resources for training and expert user support, particularly training scientists in use of new technology. For example, moving to centralised computers to increase efficiency will require sufficient training to encourage people with little experience working with large HPC systems to shift from the setup they are used to.

² [The-Sixth-Carbon-Budget-The-UKs-path-to-Net-Zero.pdf \(theccc.org.uk\)](https://www.theccc.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/The-Sixth-Carbon-Budget-The-UKs-path-to-Net-Zero.pdf)

Furthermore, the roadmap to net zero will pass through unexplored territory and training material will need to be regularly updated with lessons learned from exploratory pathfinder projects at UKRI and elsewhere.

Recognising our shared responsibility

The first vital step to transformational change is raising awareness of the importance of implementing net zero targets in global efforts to tackle the climate crisis we are in. This requires mandating and empowering all staff (from student to CEO) to take proportionate action to drive change and reduce the environmental impact of their work.

The crisis that faces us in climate and biodiversity needs to be reflected in every grant application as a key element of ethical and societal responsibility. In addition, spending decisions must include a proportionate assessment of their impact on the UKRI carbon budget and on the implementation of the Net Zero policy.

Currently, there is little or no requirement for researchers to consider the climate and sustainability impacts of their work. Furthermore, in most cases, staff do not have the tools and knowledge at hand to tackle this. Policies and requirements for net zero should be paired with adequate training to not just increase awareness and understanding of the implications of climate change and the net zero policy, but also to provide technical competence to deliver change.

It is vital that the response mandated is proportionate to the size and environmental impacts of projects whilst also keeping in mind the cumulative power of small changes. For many who are acutely aware of the urgency to take climate action, knowing what to do to make a difference can be a challenge and a burden. Empowering individuals to understand the positive actions they can take to reduce the climate impact of their work, and encouraging knowledge and ideas sharing, can reduce the mental burden of the crisis we face.

'Equity and justice are central to the ethos of UKRI and to the net zero ambition.'

Supporting Recommendations

A general discussion of the recommendations can be found in section 3.2 of the [Net Zero DRI Scoping Project's final technical report: Sustainability in Digital Research Infrastructure](#)³. A full list of the recommendations can be found in Appendix 3 of the final report and in addition can be accessed via this [spreadsheet](#).

Recommendations regarding proportionate response

'Equity and justice are central to the ethos of UKRI and to the net zero ambition.'

'There is a further ethical dimension to net zero. Institutional net zero policies should not block the wider societal pathway to net zero, for instance by consuming a disproportionate quantity of limited renewable energy resources.'

'Recognition of shared responsibility: mandate and empower all staff (from student to CEO) to take proportionate action to drive change and reduce the environmental impact of their work; community building; encourage discussion among colleagues and learn from others to foster positive changes in behaviour.'

Recommendation 2: Leverage soft capacity to accelerate change through consensus. UKRI should use its capacity in social sciences, arts and humanities, and in economics, to understand the range of societal views, the avenues of consensus which open-up potential for accelerating transition and the emerging (or exploding) discords which can block or reverse change

Recommendation 5: Blending the discipline categorisations of infrastructure and research Steps must be taken to minimise barriers to the adoption of potential efficiencies arising from new technologies in hardware and software, e.g. ensuring adequate cross over between experts of science and experts of technology

Recommendation 168: Ensure collective responsibility for Net Zero DRI (i) move towards an empowered and equitable research community, bringing top-down and grass-roots actions together (ii) develop a shared and accessible body of knowledge to support collective action, avoiding silos of practice

Recommendation 21: Impact of research on environmental sustainability. There is currently no requirement for researchers to consider that their research could have a negative impact on sustainability. The existential crises that face us in climate and biodiversity need to be reflected in every grant application as a key element of ethical and societal responsibility.

Recommendation 162: Training of staff at all levels is needed, both to increase awareness and understanding of the implications of climate change and the net zero policy, and to provide technical competence to deliver change. Training needs to be backed by an active programme of learning and discovery. The roadmap to net zero will pass through unexplored territory and training material will need to be regularly updated with lessons learned from exploratory pathfinder projects at UKRI and elsewhere

Recommendation 157: All spending decisions must include a proportionate assessment of their impact on the UKRI carbon budget and on the implementation of the Net Zero policy. In most cases staff do not have the tools and knowledge at hand, so work on training (recommendation 3.1) and standards (recommendation 1.2)

³ Juckes, M., Bane, M., Bulpett, J., Cartmell, K., MacFarlane, M., MacRae, M., Owen, A., Pascoe, C., & Townsend, P. (2023). Sustainability in Digital Research Infrastructure: UKRI Net Zero DRI Scoping Project final technical report. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8199984>

Recommendation 160: UKRI must take a proactive approach to ensuring that net zero policy does not disrupt research programmes and that prioritisation of low carbon investment and purchasing options does not have a disproportionate negative impact.

Recommendation 97: Future engagement with DRI contacts should take into account the relative size and impact of different facilities. The amount of detail required from each component of the DRI should be proportional to the potential impact of making policy and system changes. NOTE: This process should be managed carefully to avoid missing opportunities where a change to a relatively small system could be significant if applied across the DRI (e.g. a change to all UKRI laptops).

Recommendation 6: Match new technologies with information that is reliable and relevant, and appropriate training and tools. Ensure the introduction of new technologies is matched by appropriate resources for training and expert user support, particularly training scientists in use of new technology.

Recommendation 12: Training for best practice for reducing the amount of energy all research requires. People need to be made aware of the environmental impact of their research and how to reduce it. Develop information campaigns to raise levels of response efficacy that small changes can make a difference to the carbon emissions it uses.